

Synthesis of Ethyl-*p*-(2-Benzoxazolyl)Phenoxyacetate and Corresponding Hydrazides

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Synthesis of ethyl-*p*-(2-benzoxazolyl)phenoxyacetate(I) and the corresponding hydrazide(II) is described. II on condensation with different aromatic aldehydes provided III which on reduction with sodiumborohydride yielded IV. The compounds have been tested *in vitro* for antibacterial and antiviral activities.

BENZOXAZOLES have been associated with trypanocidal¹, anticonvulsant², antitubercular and antifungal³ activities. On the other hand a large number of hydrazides and related compounds have been reported to be of biological interest⁴⁻⁶. It was therefore considered worthwhile to synthesise the title products incorporating benzoxazole nucleus (Scheme 1).

Experimental

Melting points were determined in open capillaries and are not corrected. Infrared spectra were recorded on Perkin-Elmer 137 G spectrophotometer in KBr.

*Ethyl-*p*-(2-benzoxazolyl)phenoxyacetate(I)*: 2-(*p*-hydroxyphenyl)benzoxazole⁷ (21.1 g, 0.1 mole) and redistilled ethylchloroacetate (12.25 g, 0.1 mole) in dry acetone were refluxed for 18 hrs in presence of anhydrous potassium carbonate (20.7 g, 0.15 mole). The reaction mixture was filtered and the ester (I) was recovered on evaporating the solvent. It was recrystallised from ethanol, m.p. 140°, yield 80%. Found: C, 68.60; N, 4.56; H, 4.95. $C_{17}H_{15}NO_4$ requires C, 68.68; N, 4.71; H, 5.05% IR (μ): 5.85 (C=O), 6.2 (C=N, ring).

p-(2-Benzoxazolyl)phenoxyacetyl hydrazide(II): Ester I (2.97 g, 0.01 mole) and hydrazine hydrate⁸ (1 ml, 0.02 mole) in absolute ethanol (50 ml) were

Scheme I

refluxed for 12 hrs. Excess of solvent was removed and the solid obtained on cooling was filtered and recrystallised from ethanol, m. p. 284°, yield 70%. Found : C, 63.50 ; N, 14.65 ; H, 4.66. $C_{15}H_{13}N_3O_3$ requires C, 63.60 ; N, 14.80 ; H, 4.59%. IR (μ) : 3.1 (NH), 5.85 (C=O), 6.2 (C=N, ring).

N-(Substituted benzylidene)-*p*-(2-benzoxazolyl)-phenoxy acetic acid hydrazides : Equimolar quantities of hydrazide (II) and a suitable aldehyde in ethanol containing three drops of glacial acetic acid were refluxed for 4 hrs⁹. The solid, separating on cooling, was filtered and recrystallised from ethanol. The compounds thus synthesised are given in the Table 1.

TABLE 1—N-(SUBSTITUTED BENZYLIDENE)-*p*-(2-BENZOXAZOLYL)PHENOXY ACETIC ACID HYDRAZIDES(III)

Sl. No.	R	m.p. °C	% Analysis N	
			Calcd.	Found
1.	Phenyl	225	11.62	11.23
2.	<i>p</i> -chlorophenyl	228	10.37	10.12
3.*	<i>p</i> -nitrophenyl	252	13.46	13.38
4.	<i>p</i> -hydroxyphenyl	260	10.84	10.70
5.	<i>o</i> -hydroxyphenyl	240	10.84	10.88
6.	<i>p</i> -hydroxy, <i>m</i> -methoxy phenyl	198	10.76	10.50
7.	<i>p</i> -methoxyphenyl	175	10.45	10.23
8.	<i>o</i> -furyl	222	11.63	11.68

Yield varied from 60-80%

* Analysis C, 63.40 ; H, 3.75 ; $C_{22}H_{16}N_4O_3$ requires C, 63.46 ; H, 3.84%.

IR(μ) : 1. 3.1(NH), 6.0(C=O), 6.2(C=N) ring, 5.90(N=C) weak.
2. 2.95(NH), 5.95(N=C) weak, 6.0(C=O), 6.2(C=N) ring.
3. 3.0(NH), 6.0(C=O), 5.95(N=C) weak, 6.2(C=N) ring.

TABLE 2—N-(SUBSTITUTED BENZYL)-*p*-(2-BENZOXAZOLYL)PHENOXY ACETIC ACID HYDRAZIDES(IV)

Sl. No.	R	m.p. °C	% Analysis N	
			Calcd.	Found
1.	Phenyl	222	11.53	11.65
2.	<i>p</i> -chlorophenyl	225	10.25	10.40
3.	<i>p</i> -nitrophenyl	245	13.25	13.22
4.	<i>p</i> -hydroxyphenyl	270	10.62	10.75
5.	<i>o</i> -hydroxyphenyl	238	10.62	10.48
6.*	<i>p</i> -hydroxy, <i>m</i> -methoxyphenyl	250	10.72	10.86
7.	<i>o</i> -furyl	205	11.25	11.46

Yields were quantitative.

* Analysis : Found 65.75 ; H, 4.85 ; $C_{22}H_{21}N_3O_3$ requires C, 65.87 ; H, 5.01%.

IR(μ) : 1. 3.0(NH) strong, 5.98(C=O), 6.2(C=N) ring.
2. 3.0(NH) strong, 5.95(C=O), 6.1(C=N) ring.

N-(Substituted benzyl)-*p*-(2-benzoxazolyl) phenoxy acetic acid hydrazides (secondary amines) : A 10% methanolic solution of sodium borohydride was added with stirring to a 10% methanolic solution of Schiff's base (III) over 30 min. The mixture was heated for half an hour. Excess of methanol was removed and the secondary amine was isolated by addition of water¹⁰. It was filtered and recrystallised. The compounds thus synthesised are given in the Table 2.

Bio-assay : Compounds 2, 3, 5 of Table 1 were tested against tobacco mosaic virus at 2 mg/ml concentration. The host virus system employed were TMV-N-tabacum var. white burley Ky⁶⁸. The compounds showed significant antiviral activity *in vitro* but not *in vivo*.

Antibacterial activity : Compounds 1, 2, 3, 5 and 8 of the Table 1 and 1, 2, 3, 5 and 7 of Table 2 have been evaluated for their inhibitory effects against three organisms ; *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Bacillus subtilis* and *Sorsena lutea* by agar diffusion technique¹¹. All tests were carried out in duplicate. The compounds showed inhibition against the organisms. Bacterial cultures maintained at Public Analytical Laboratory to U. P. Govt. were used.

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